

FILM AS A PEDAGOGICAL TOOL IN ANTHROPOLOGY AND INTERIOR DESIGN

Byrad Yyelland^{1*}, Johan Granberg²

¹ Dr., Virginia Commonwealth University Qatar, QATAR, bayyelland@vcu.edu

² Dr., Virginia Commonwealth University Qatar, QATAR, eigranberg@vcu.edu

Abstract

This study presents reflective analyses of filmmaking as a pedagogical tool within two interior design courses and multiple sections of an introductory anthropology course offered at an American design school branch campus in Qatar. In this paper, the authors present analyses of pedagogical pros and cons as noted through three types of filmmaking: student-made fiction, instructor-made documentary, and film inserted into the design process. In the first example, undergraduate interior design students worked with professional film crews to create a trilogy of mini-films based on The Three Musketeers story-line. The script was written by the instructor of the course who is also one of the authors of this presentation. For this exercise, students created the sets and costumes, assisted with lighting and sound, and acted all roles. The second example features pedagogic contributions of a 25-minute documentary of life in a Brazilian favela, the culmination of a multi-year ethnographic study conducted by the authors. Third, interior design students were taught how to create and conduct interviews as preparation for designing for a community. They then conducted site analyses through the lens of the camera and presented the final outcomes via 3-5 minute design films. Through analyses of three cinematic experiences in the classroom, the authors offer post-production insights into the power of filmmaking as a pedagogical praxis when students are directly involved and when they are not, but they see their professors on screen and can ask questions about the filmmaking experiences and processes. These insights include analysis from the combined lenses of design theory and sociocultural anthropology analyses of film content and production from start to finish, as pedagogical mechanisms and processes. Findings include a profound increase in the depth and breadth of student learning regarding the realities of set design ideation, construction and application versus theory; deep experiential learning of film production' the influences of culture upon young women portraying strongly counter-cultural roles of warriors in a strongly patriarchal society; filmmaking praxis as it relates with trying to get the intended point across to the audience; collective collaboration on film production; culture and social class in a Rio de Janeiro favela; the role and impact of the key informant; how to properly access and present the voice of the subject; the types of problems that can arise in ethnographic research; and the impact of framing the subject when creating a 3-5 minute design film.

Keywords: Filmmaking, pedagogy, ethnography, student research, design theory, anthropology